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Index of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CMOC - Context-mechanism-outcome pattern configuration

ICCT - Internal Centre for Counter-Terrorism

MAUT - Multi-attribute evaluation technique

UNICRI - United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute

UNODC - United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime

Executive summary

The current report is part of the WayOut - “Integrated Exit Programme for Prison and Probation” projects’ Work Package 3 - Evaluation framework of exit programmes. Before the actual development of an evaluation framework (that will be done in the next deliverable), the current deliverable reviews the literature on evaluation methods for exit programmes (or similar intervention programmes). After problematising on the importance of evaluation for intervention programmes, the report presents methods that can be used for the evaluation of these programmes. Multi-attribute evaluation, theory-based evaluation, contribution analysis, realist evaluation, and structural integrity assessment are presented as potentially useful evaluation methods for exit programmes. Options regarding evaluation design are presented. Different evaluation focus (i.e., impact, mechanism, process, economic) and instruments that can be used for the evaluation are also presented.

The report ends with conclusions that can be relevant for the development of the evaluation framework.

1. Introduction

In the WayOut WP3, we aim to develop a framework for the evaluation of exit programmes. The existing literature on how to evaluate intervention programmes, and specifically exit programmes (whenever literature exists on this particular topic), will be reviewed in the current deliverable. Besides that, when developing the framework, feasibility of the proposed strategy will be considered, taking into consideration the project's timeframe, as well as the number of exit strategies that will be reviewed. These goals are aligned with the WayOut goal of collecting and reviewing/evaluating existing EXIT programmes while developing an innovative EXIT programmes.

Taking into consideration that the literature stresses the importance of tailor-made, personalised exit programmes, implying a different set of interventions for each case, challenges arise in the evaluation of exit programmes, namely in comparativeness, therefore increasing the need for “an evaluation method that can deal with different contextual circumstances” (Gielen, 2018, p. 455).

In order to have a critical view of the evaluations methods presented, it is important to know some quality criteria for EXIT programme, such as the ones summarised by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (cf. UNODC, 2016), United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UNICRI) and the Internal Centre for Counter-Terrorism (ICCT) experts¹. The “Rome Memorandum on Good Practices for Rehabilitation and Reintegration of Violent Extremist Offenders” presents 25 good practices of which 5 focus on the prison context and 7 focus on the role of different actors in prisons. The document starts with a general good practice (clear definition of goals and objectives of the programmes; and the development of success/failure indicators) and then proceeds to the good practices in the prison context and related with different professionals in this context. Without being exhaustive, we summarise the good practices as follows (Global Counterterrorism Forum, 2011).

Related with the prison context:

- Offer good prison conditions: avoid extra-judicial punishment²; address problems with overcrowding, lack of resources or poor services in order to build a proper environment for the implementation of the programmes;
- Develop an effective intake, assessment and classification system for new inmates: the assessment at intake will be crucial to the design of effective interventions; assessment of individual needs should be periodically implemented and can have consequences on inmates' placement (i.e., segregation vs integration);
- Ensure adequate training of all relevant staff: prison staff working with extremist inmates should have the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes to contribute to the successful implementation of the programme;
- Introduction of control mechanisms: when needed, and in accordance with the level of threat, monitoring measures (i.e., control inmate's internal/external communication) can be implemented.

¹ Besides the more technical and specialised documents mentioned, it is also important to know the more general prison rules such as the “Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners” (Nelson Mandela Rules).

² During the review processes the partners mentioned that not only this should be achieved but also there is a need to guarantee fair trials as a basis for sentencing;

Related with the role of different actors in prisons:

- Incorporation of cross-disciplinary experts in the programme: considering the wide range of motivation factors that played a role in the individuals radicalisation process; the key role played by psychologists should be acknowledged with their full integration in the programmes;
- Prison officers should understand the rehabilitation process, contributing to support the programme and avoiding counterproductive actions;
- Consider the integration of scholars in the programme: trained scholars can engage in extensive dialogue with inmates that, as a consequence, can potentially question their extremist worldview;
- Consider the inclusion of victims in the rehabilitation process: whenever this is beneficial to the victims well-being and if there is a potential beneficial for the perpetrator;
- Consider the inclusion of former, de-radicalised terrorists;
- Whenever possible and appropriate, consider the inclusion of charismatic community members.

Several good practices related with the reintegration component are also considered, such as the inclusion of cognitive skills programmes, basic education courses, vocational skills training, recognition of educational/training achievements, use of incentives for participation, development of aftercare programmes, post-release protective measures (when needed), formal/informal post-monitoring, inclusion of family members in the rehabilitation programme, positive and welcoming community environment.

Therefore, knowing these good practices helps us know what to look for in the programmes, when designing an evaluation method.

This deliverable is structure as follows:

- **Section 2 - Evaluation methods for exit programmes.** At first, we will review the literature on methods suitable for the evaluation of exit programmes, providing the ground for the upcoming work;
- **Section 3 - Evaluation focus and instruments.** In this section we will emphasise the different focus that the evaluation can have as well as instruments that can be used.
- **Section 4 - Conclusions.** Lastly, main conclusions will be drawn upon the previous sections findings, which will be key for the development of the proposed framework.

2. Evaluation methods for exit programmes

Assuming that evaluation of intervention/exit programmes is key to several domains (e.g., decisions about the programmes; fine-tuning programmes), one needs to know which methodologies are available and are considered appropriate to this endeavour. It is also important to recognise the challenges related with the evaluation of these programmes. For instance, as stated by Horgan and Braddock (2010), it is not expected that negative outcomes are made public by governmental organisation implementing these programmes. On other hand, it is also challenging to ensure that evaluators will have the needed access to relevant outcome data (Williams & Kleinman, 2014). According to Lipsey, Petrie, Weisburd, and Gottfredson (2006),

referring to the evaluation of anti-crime programmes, state that data may be difficult to access because programme managers may not be willing to share outcome data with the evaluators for several reasons (ethical reasons; seeing outcome data as proprietary) and individuals may fail to answer to evaluation questionnaires or provide incomplete data.

In the paper “*A Literature Review on Methodology used in Evaluating Effects of Preventive and De-radicalisation Interventions*”, Feddes and Gallucci (2015) found that a vast majority of the analysed manuscripts didn’t present any quantitative/qualitative empirical data (that was the case in 88% of the manuscripts) related with the evaluation of the programmes. The authors added that “instruments and methods used were often not specified. Cross-sectional methods have been used most often. This is problematic as many interventions have a long-term prevention or restoration focus. In addition, it was found that when used, evaluations often make use of a single instrument. An additional finding is that existing interventions mainly focus on the individual level whereby attention for effects on a group level is lacking” (p. 17), arguing for the need of more rigorous, multi-method approach to the assessment of deradicalisation programmes. This can be achieved with the combination of methods such as interviews, surveys, observations and indicators of recidivism instead of not running an evaluation of the programme or run a poor evaluation focused on a single instrument or method. Therefore, with the use of triangulation (i.e., combination of multiple methods and data sources) an increase in the validity of the evaluation findings is guaranteed (Mathison, 1988).

Multi-attribute evaluation

According to Horgan and Braddock’s (2010) perspective, multi-attribute evaluation technique (MAUT) should be used as it represents the “most suitable evaluation framework with which to examine terrorism risk reduction initiatives” (p. 284). This technique allows evaluators to:

- 1) Do comparative assessment (i.e., compare between different programmes);
- 2) Evaluate the ongoing performance of a programme;
- 3) Evaluate programmes that need fine-tuning;
- 4) Determine which - out of a number of initiatives or programmes - is the most appropriate given the needs, goals, and available resources.

Some initial questions should be made, such as:

- 1) What function does the evaluation has? That means, define if the evaluation will be run in order to monitor the programme(s), or fine-tuning them and taking policy decisions such as choosing between different programmes;
- 2) What is the object of the evaluation? That is, what will we evaluate?
- 3) Who are the stakeholders? In this approach, stakeholder will have a key role since they will be responsible to define the attributes that will be used in the evaluation process.

MAUT steps are defined by Edwards and Newman (1982). The authors consider the following seven steps for the implementation of this evaluation technique:

- 1) Identify the object and functions of the evaluation;
- 2) Identify the stakeholders;
- 3) Elicit the value dimensions / attributes from the stakeholders;
- 4) For each stakeholder, assess the relative importance (weights) of each attribute;
- 5) Ascertain how well each object (e.g., intervention programme) serves each attribute;

- 6) Aggregate evaluations;
- 7) Perform sensitivity analysis.

Despite the importance of this evaluation technique, the complexity of its implementation is not compatible with WayOut's timetable. Moreover, some criticisms on the method arise, since it is very pragmatic and has a strong focus on policy making and stakeholders, and little or no room is left for the evaluation of the relevance of the programme goals, of the programme social impact.

However, some steps (such as the identification of stakeholders and the elicitation of evaluation attributes from them) of this technique are useful and, therefore, can be incorporated in the development of our framework though the incorporation of the mentioned steps' activities.

Theory-based evaluation

Theory-based evaluation is a useful evaluation method that help us know more than the outcomes about an intervention programme, through the elicitation of programme designers' "theories about how the programme is expected to work" (Weiss, 1997, p. 51). Defining the concept based on the theory-based evaluation literature, Birckmayer and Weiss (2000) state that, in this evaluation, the assumptions on which the programme is based are explored in a detailed way. The exploration of the programme theory can follow steps such as: "what activities are being conducted, what effect each particular activity will have, what the program does next, what the expected response is, what happens next, and so on, to the expected outcomes" (Birckmayer & Weiss, 2000, p. 408). This type of evaluation can be useful in the field of exit programmes since "it provides insight into what interventions and programmes might work in countering radicalisation, without an actual evaluation having to be conducted" (Gielen, 2017, p. 3).

Characteristics of the theory-based evaluation, as summarised by Leeuw (2012), are:

- Focus on the programme theory (i.e., assumptions);
- Conceptual explanation of the programme theory and empirical investigation of programme intended/observed outcomes;
- Importance of mechanisms and how they are linked with the context and outcomes;
- Use of different methods to test the assumptions/theory and improve it.

Implementing a theory-based evaluation is very demanding both in time and staff skills, leading to limitations related with its application in small projects that may lack the needed time and which staff may need some of the needed skills (Rogers, Petrosino, Huebner, & Hacsí, 2000).

Contribution analysis

Contribution analysis is a typology of theory-based evaluation that explores programmes' contribution to the observed results. In fact, when experimental or quasi-experimental designs can't be implemented, a doubt remains about the causality of the observed results, that is, if they can be explained by the intervention itself or if it can be explained by other factor(s). Causality between the implementation of an intervention programme and the observed results is then inferred from a series of evidence that is collected (Leeuw, 2012; Mayne, 2008):

- 1) The programme is based on solid and plausible assumptions that comprise a theory of

- change on which key players agree upon;
- 2) The foreseen activities of the intervention programme were implemented;
- 3) There is evidence that the expected chain of results occurred;
- 4) Other influencing factors were considered and:
 - a. they didn't have an influence on the programme;
 - b. they had a significant contribution to the programme (which was acknowledged).

Implementation of contribution analysis follows six iterative steps (Mayne, 2008):

- i) **Set out the attribution problem to be addressed:** during this first step, attribution is questioned, meaning that evaluators do not pre-assume that effects that occurred were caused by the intervention programme; therefore, questions such as “to what extent the programme has caused this outcome” arise at this stage.
- ii) **Develop a theory of change and ascertain risks to it:** during this step, evaluators build a theory of change (i.e., how the programme is supposed to achieve the desired results), based on assumptions, and a results chain (i.e., what will be the immediate, intermediate and final outcomes if the assumptions come true).
- iii) **Gather existing evidence:** the collected evidence should include observed results and activities (i.e., if the results occurred or not; programme implementation as planned), assumptions about the theory of change (i.e., evidence about the validity of the theory of change), and other influencing factors (i.e., if other potentially influential factors were presented);
- iv) **Assemble and assess the contribution story, and challenges to it:** with the data gathered from individuals implementing the programme and experts a contribution story can be developed. How strong the links in the results chain are, how credible is the overall contribution story, what weaknesses does the story has and if stakeholders agree with it are points to be discussed at this point.
- v) **Seek additional evidence:** considering how robust is the contribution story, the evaluator can look for new data, review the theory of change and gathering more evidence, using multiple approaches such as surveys, case studies, evaluating more deeply a component of the programme with a weak performance, and tracking variations (in time and/or location) in project's implementation.
- vi) **Revise and strengthen the contribution story:** using the additional evidence, the previous contributions story developing in the fourth step can now be revised and improved, ending in a more credible story.

After *step vi*), the evaluator can return to *step iv*), reassembling the contribution story based on the additional evidence collected.

Limitations of the contribution analysis may include the nonidentification of programme outcomes or routes that were not foreseen by the contribution story (Baruch & Gorp, 2018).

Realist evaluation

Evaluating counter-violent extremism studies, Gielen (2017) advocates the use of **realist evaluation**, that tries to answer the questions “what works, for whom, in which context, and how?” (p. 2). The author reviews 73 studies, of which 15 focus on deradicalisation, disengagement, rehabilitation or reintegration (i.e., exit programmes). These studies use process evaluation,

theory-driven evaluation or a combination of both. Realist evaluation is a theory-driven approach that “considers that programmes and interventions are based on an underlying programme theory, which describes how, under which conditions, and for whom the intervention is expected to lead to its desired outcomes” (Sim & Gorp, 2018, p. 139). The cited authors state that this method can be used to understand how programmes work, highlighting four related concepts:

- 1) Mechanism - refers to what creates any effects in an intervention (e.g., dynamic between the facilitator and the participants);
- 2) Context - that is, under which conditions (relevant for the programme mechanism) is the intervention being implemented?
- 3) Outcome patterns - refers to the intended and unintended consequences of the intervention programme (as a combination of the different mechanisms and contexts);
- 4) Context-mechanism-outcome pattern configuration (CMOC) - encompasses the assessment of different mechanisms and contexts in order to predict and explain the diversity of outcome patterns.

According to the cited authors, a “realist evaluation would construct CMOC models of how the programme works that can be tested empirically” (p. 140), reaching useful findings for practitioners and policy makers and being useful for the evaluations of complex programmes such as exit programmes.

Manzano (2016) explores the role of realist interviews for realist evaluation. Realist interview can be described as a theory-drive interview that intends to investigate theoretical propositions (instead of exploring aspects and concepts as it happens with open or semi-structured interviews). The author suggests three phases for the realist interviews:

- 1) Theory gleaning interviews: in this first interviews, interviewees are expected to help the evaluation articulating first order theories, that is, the theories “that identify how the contextual circumstances of some users/programmes may impact behaviour and effectiveness” (p. 354);
- 2) Theory refinement: follow-up interviews that allow the evaluator to explore the programme nuances with tailor-made questions to refine the specific outcome patterns;
- 3) Theory consolidation: proceeds with the previous refinement of the candidate theories that were not preciously discounted. The interviewee will provide insights that will allow the validation of theories as well as falsifying examples, helping in the consolidation stage.

Structural Integrity Assessment

Reflecting on the evaluation of exit programmes, Koehler (2017) argues in favor of a structural integrity assessment of these interventions over more traditional impact or process evaluation. Having the Rome Memorandum (briefly described in the introduction section) as a starting point, the author develops structural integrity assessment guidelines, considering several aspects of exit programmes, such as programme design, staff and staff straining, handling and categorization of participants, care and advisory services, quality assurance and transparency. In a more detailed way, we have:

- **Regarding programme design:**
 - There is a clear definition of the programme aims;
 - Existence of an “effective case management registration, reception and

- categorisation system” (p. 26);
 - Low threshold for initial contact;
 - “provide a direct contact person for the initial conversation” (p. 27);
 - Existence of an interdisciplinary case management team and experts in the field of psychology;
 - The use of “former extremists and terrorists as case workers” (p. 27);
 - Provide case workers with clear guidelines and quality standards related with their activity;
 - Provide to the disengaging radical the victims’ perspective/experience;
 - Include in the intervention design the perspective of the town/city/district where the person will be reintegrated.
- **Regarding staff and staff training:**
 - Previous training of caseworkers or on-the-job training, using training materials that will be available for evaluators;
 - Staff feedback on training content should be encouraged;
 - Provide ethical guidelines for caseworkers;
 - Solid recruitment of case workers;
 - Staff assessment according to the quality of the developed work;
 - Discussion of cases in regular team meetings;
 - Effective supervision of caseworkers.
- **Handling and categorization of participants:**
 - Clear definition of the target group;
 - Set clear exclusion criteria and their application;
 - Define participants’ risk factors and corresponding procedures;
 - Standardised recording of the implemented programme methods and their impact on the risk factors;
 - Effective case documentation system, allowing the handover of a case among staff members.
- **Care and advisory services:**
 - Emphasize the treatment of individual radicalization factors;
 - Work/strengthen participants cognitive abilities;
 - Provide general vocational education;
 - Planning and implementing protective measures for participants (i.e., avoid any retaliation from former group or enemies);
 - Adjust intervention’s intensity and programme resources according to the participant’s risk level;
 - comprehensive and up-to-date handbook for all programme processes;
 - gather feedback from participants;
 - caseworkers’ documentation of any negative effects of the advisory work done;
 - test the chosen methods for any possible negative effects at the beginning of the programme;
 - set criteria for ending the individual intervention programme; when accomplished, close the case as previously planned and organize a follow-up session with caseworkers providing feedback for the programme;

- record the ratio of closed cases / uncompleted cases;
 - involvement of the participant’s affective environment (i.e., relatives, friends).
- **Quality Assurance**
 - Internal quality assurance (e.g., test of caseworkers’ knowledge; regular reports done by caseworkers are submitted to programme managers);
 - Evaluate unsuccessful cases and keep available statistics on known relapses;
 - Regular external evaluations of different aspects of the programme done by third parties;
 - Critical and transparent dialogue related with programme implementation weaknesses and possible structural problems.

Regarding transparency, Koehler (2017) presents a list of 10 points related with things such as processes, financing (e.g, use of funds) and personnel structure (e.g, employees, volunteers) of the implementing organization that should be available for being unequivocal regarding the organization that is running the programme, the programme itself and its implementation.

Overall, these standards can then be used to ensure proper evaluation of exit programmes. Moreover, these measurable criterion “demonstrate a high correlation with low recidivism rates, drop-out rates and lasting behavioural changes among participants” (Koehler, 2017, p. 22) in intervention programmes in different fields (e.g., psychology, criminology), representing therefore useful indicators for the assessment of exit programmes.

Evaluation design, focus and instruments

Besides the methodologies being used for the assessment of the exit programmes, it is also important to consider the different evaluation design options that are available, as well as the foci of the evaluation that is being implemented.

Regarding the design of the evaluation, 5 common types of evaluation design are mentioned in the literature (Helmus et al., 2017):

- 1) Retrospective Pre-/Post-intervention evaluation: involving participants in the programme at one point in time, asking them to report changes in skills, knowledge and behavior attributed to the programme implementation;
- 2) Pre-/Post-intervention evaluation: as the name implies, it comprises the collection of data among participants before the programme starts and after the programme ends;
- 3) Interrupted time-series analysis: use secondary data collected at multiple times to analyse potential changes in the participants;
- 4) Pre-/Post-intervention evaluation with comparison group: involves the collection of pre and post programme data with participants as well as the collection of pre and post programme data with a groups which composition is similar to the participants;
- 5) Pre-/Post-intervention evaluation with control group: considers data collected before and after the programme implementation with participants that actually went through the intervention (experimental group) as opposed to participants that didn’t went through the progame (control group)³.

³ This option implies that participants are randomly assigned to the mentioned groups.

The different evaluation designs led to the importance of including evaluation in the programme design since evaluation moments can occur even before the programme starts.

Regarding the focus of the evaluation, [According to Feddes and Gallucci \(2015\)](#), we can consider 4 different foci:

- Impact: this happens when the evaluation focus is on the effect of the intervention;
- Mechanism: when the intervention focusses on “why the intervention was considered effective” (p. 12);
- Process: when the assessment focus on the implementation of the programme (how);
- Economic: when the assessment of the programme takes into consideration the underlying financial costs.

A distinction between impact and process evaluation can also be found on [Koehler \(2017\)](#) report, where the cited author states that “whilst an impact evaluation pursues the aim of verifying whether a specific project actually achieved the desired effect (e.g., deradicalising individuals), process evaluation aims to ascertain whether the programme does effectively what it was designed to do” (p. 21). Still according to the author, to develop an effective process evaluation, one needs to construct and establish objective quality standards in order not to compromise the entire evaluation and avoid an evaluation solely based on inputs from the programme that are likely to be biased, since they represent only one possible view on how successful the programme was. Therefore, triangulation is strongly advised.

Process evaluation data can include satisfaction surveys to participants, tracking participation or attendance to the intervention, collecting sociodemographic data of participants and other measures of implementation activity (e.g., adherence to the programme curriculum) ([Helmus et al., 2017](#)). On other hand, impact evaluation have been measured with constructs such as support for extremism, outgroup hostility, anger, depression, and social support ([Helmus et al., 2017](#)).

Regarding the instruments used in the assessment process, exit programmes seem to be evaluated with the use of questionnaires, interviews, observation and techniques such as focus group ([Feddes & Gallucci, 2015](#)). According to the literature (e.g., [Feddes & Gallucci, 2015](#); [Manzano, 2016](#)), it is also important to use more than one instrument in the assessment of a programme, that is, as an example, combining in the evaluation of a programme the use of questionnaires and interviews.

3. Conclusions

This literature review on evaluation methods for exit programmes provides the theoretical framework for designing evaluations for exit interventions. Starting with the evaluation methods for exit programmes, we can conclude that no single method stands out in the literature and each method has its own number of pros and cons. While some authors (e.g., Horgan & Braddock, 2010) argue in favour of MAUT - focusing on its strengths in guiding the development of future interventions -, others lean towards realist evaluation - advocating its advantages due to the combination of the context and mechanism's effects on the intervention outcomes - (e.g., Gielen, 2017) or contribution analysis - a theory-based evaluation type that aims at finding the real contribution of the intervention to the observable outcomes - (e.g., Mayne, 2008). However, some key ideas are found across different authors. Namely, the need for a multi-method approach, that can be achieved with the combination of observation, interviews, questionnaires, among others, raises some agreement in the field (e.g., Feddes & Gallucci, 2015; Manzano, 2016). The same happens with the importance of having a well-designed and structured programme, with a coherent set of goals, implemented by a skilful multidisciplinary team. These key ideas reflect some of the good practices presented in the Rome Memorandum and, together, represent a starting point for the development of an evaluation framework. Regarding the evaluation focus, it is important to notice that while it is more common to think about the impact of an intervention (i.e., what was the effect of the intervention), we should not neglect the importance of evaluating the mechanisms, process and the financial costs related with running an exit programme.

Considering that researchers and practitioners favour a personalised approach to exit programmes/interventions, that targets participants' needs - which makes it difficult for an evaluation method to perfectly fit the evaluation purposes of different programmes/interventions - the key aspects summarised in this report will help designing better evaluation strategies for exit programmes/interventions. Therefore, the present report, reviewing the literature in the field of exit programmes, provides a valuable contribution for the development of an evaluation framework and improve the design of exit programmes.

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